

1 Uncovering the electronic state interplay at metal oxide
2 electron transport layer/non-fullerene acceptor
3 interfaces in stable organic photovoltaic devices

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16 ABSTRACT

17 The implementation of sputter-deposited TiO_x as an electron transport layer in non-fullerene acceptor
18 based organic photovoltaics has been shown to significantly increase the long-term stability of
19 devices compared to conventional solution-processed ZnO, due to a decreased photo-catalytic activity

20 of the sputtered TiO_x . In this work, we utilize synchrotron-based photoemission and absorption
21 spectroscopies to investigate the interface between the electron transport layer, TiO_x prepared by
22 magnetron sputtering, and the non-fullerene acceptor, ITIC, prepared in-situ by spray deposition, to
23 study the electronic state interplay and defect states at this interface. This is used to unveil the
24 mechanisms behind the decreased photo-catalytic activity of the sputter-deposited TiO_x , and thereby
25 also the increased stability of the organic solar cell devices. The results have been compared to similar
26 measurements on anatase TiO_x , since anatase TiO_x is known to have a strong photo-catalytic activity.
27 We show that the deposition of ITIC on top of the sputter-deposited TiO_x results in an oxidation of
28 Ti^{3+} species in the TiO_x , and leads to the emergence of a new O1s peak that can be attributed to the
29 oxygen in ITIC. In addition, increasing the thickness of ITIC on TiO_x leads to a shift in the O1s and
30 C1s core levels towards higher binding energies, which is consistent with electron transfer at the
31 interface. Resonant photoemission at the Ti L-edge shows that oxygen vacancies in sputtered TiO_x
32 lie mostly in the surface region, which contrasts the anatase TiO_x where an equal distribution between
33 surface and sub-surface oxygen vacancies is observed. Furthermore, it is shown that the sub-surface
34 oxygen vacancies in sputtered TiO_x are strongly reduced after ITIC deposition, which can reduce the
35 photo-catalytic activity of the oxide, while the oxygen vacancies in model anatase TiO_x are not
36 affected upon ITIC deposition. This difference can explain the inferior photo-catalytic activity of the
37 sputter-deposited TiO_x , and thereby also the increased stability of devices with sputter-deposited TiO_x
38 used as an electron transport layer.

39 **KEYWORDS:** Non-fullerene acceptors, Metal oxide interfaces, photoemission, energy level
40 alignment, organic photovoltaics

41 **INTRODUCTION**

42 The implementation of non-fullerene acceptors (NFAs) in organic photovoltaics (OPVs) has resulted
43 in a significant enhancement of their power conversion efficiency (PCE), which has recently
44 surpassed 19 %¹. Even though the PCE of OPVs has reached values closer to Si-based PV, they still
45 lack behind when it comes to long-term stability^{2,3}. In fact, a well-known stability issue in new high
46 performing organic and hybrid solar cells is UV-induced photodegradation of the active layer material
47 at the metal oxide electron transport layers (ETLs), demonstrated recently for both TiO_x and ZnO
48 ETLs due to their strong photocatalytic activity^{4,5}. The photocatalytic activity of ZnO and TiO_x is
49 known to be depending on the concentration of surface defects, which thus contributes to the
50 degradation of the active layer material at the metal oxide interface. When these metal oxide ETLs
51 are exposed to UV-light, electron-hole pairs are generated, and the resulting charge carriers take part
52 in reduction-oxidation reactions with adsorbed water at defect sites (oxygen vacancies) on the metal
53 oxide surface. These reactions lead to the formation of hydroxyl radicals, which can cause
54 decomposition of the organic molecules⁴. While there has been several strategies to passivate such
55 surface defects or suppress the photocatalytic activity of NFAs on ZnO to improve photostability^{6,7,8,}
56 ⁹, a more elegant and also practical approach is to overcome this degradation by developing metal
57 oxide ETLs that possess lower photocatalytic activity, such as SnO₂⁹. In this context, we have recently
58 shown that tuning the surface oxygen content in sputter-deposited TiO_x ETLs enhance the long-term
59 stability of PBDB-T:ITIC based OPV devices significantly, when compared to conventional solution-
60 processed metal oxide ETLs, due to reduced photocatalytic decomposition of the NFA molecule ITIC
61 at the metal oxide ETL¹⁰. This is significant since TiO_x is a commonly used ETL material in both
62 organic and hybrid solar cells, which is known to have a high photocatalytic activity.

63 Non-fullerene acceptors such as ITIC have previously been investigated by photoemission and
64 absorption spectroscopy^{11,12}. However, at this point, such studies have only been conducted on ex-
65 situ prepared NFAs. In this study we have compared in-situ prepared ITIC by spray coating in

66 vacuum, with ex-situ prepared ITIC by spin-coating in a nitrogen-filled glovebox. Detailed in-situ
67 photoemission and absorption spectroscopy interface studies are relevant, as they can shed more light
68 on the interface properties between TiO_x and ITIC, including the detailed surface and interface
69 properties potentially leading to interfacial degradation.

70 In this study, we have used X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), Near-edge X-ray Absorption
71 Fine Structure (NEXAFS), and resonant photoemission spectroscopy (RESPES) to study the core
72 levels, highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO), lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO)
73 levels, and defect states at the in-situ prepared TiO_x /ITIC interface, in order to uncover the electronic
74 interplay at this interface. This allows us to understand the mechanisms behind the increased device
75 stability and decreased photocatalytic degradation of ITIC in sputtered TiO_x /ITIC based OPV devices.
76 We found that deposition of ITIC on sputtered TiO_x (showing limited photocatalytic degradation in
77 PBDB-T:ITIC/ TiO_x devices¹⁰) results in oxidation of Ti^{3+} species, and the emergence of a new O1s
78 peak due to the oxygen in ITIC, which is consistent with electron transfer at the interface. We also
79 show that the deposition of ITIC moves the VBM closer to the Fermi level at the interface. In addition,
80 RESPES measurements show that ITIC deposition results in partial quenching of the Ti 3d states.

81 The results have been compared to similar measurements performed on a natural anatase TiO_x single
82 crystal, since anatase TiO_x is known to have a strong photocatalytic activity, and therefore represent
83 a proper reference sample for this study. We found that the sub-surface defects in sputter deposited
84 TiO_x are partially quenched after ITIC deposition whereas they remain unaffected in anatase TiO_x .
85 Thus, after ITIC deposition, both surface and sub-surface vacancies are observed for both sputtered
86 and anatase TiO_x , however, with a different ratio for the two TiO_x samples leading to different surface
87 properties that could explain their difference in photocatalytic behavior.

88 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

89 Three thicknesses of ITIC were quantified by the overlayer method¹³ on top of the sputtered TiO_x
90 after spray deposition of ITIC, which were 0.5 nm, 0.9 nm and 1.8 nm. Ti 2p, O1s and C1s core level
91 spectra were recorded with a photon energy of 650 eV on TiO_x, before and after deposition of ITIC.
92 These spectra can be seen in figure 1. The core level spectra show that the overall intensity of Ti 2p
93 and O1s decreases, and the C1s intensity increases with increasing ITIC thickness, confirming
94 successful deposition of an overlayer. The presence of ITIC was confirmed by NEXAFS, where sulfur
95 and nitrogen were observed (see SI).

96 After subsequent annealing under oxygen (see Experimental Section), the Ti 2p core level spectrum
97 for bare sputtered TiO_x shows two main peaks at 459.24 eV and 465.00 eV, corresponding to Ti 2p_{3/2}
98 and Ti2p_{1/2} spin-doublet components of Ti⁴⁺, respectively^{14,15}. A lower binding energy shoulder at
99 457.91 eV corresponds to Ti 2p_{3/2} signal from reduced Ti³⁺ species^{14,15}. After ITIC deposition, the
100 main Ti 2p feature is observed at 459.17 eV, and the Ti³⁺ is notably reduced indicating oxidation of
101 titanium species. Indeed, the bare TiO_x film has 26.2% Ti³⁺, which is reduced to 9.6 % after deposition
102 of 0.5 nm of ITIC, and further to 0 % after deposition of 1.8 nm of ITIC.

103 The O1s spectrum for bare TiO_x shows a main feature around 530.70 eV, which can be attributed to
104 lattice oxygen participating in Ti⁴⁺-O bonds¹⁴⁻¹⁶. An additional feature centered at 531.90 eV can be
105 attributed to surface adsorbed OH species^{14, 15, 17}, and an additional feature at 533.31 eV, can be
106 attributed to adsorbed water¹⁸. After deposition of 0.5 nm and 0.9 nm of ITIC, a new feature at 532.40
107 eV develops due to the oxygen of ITIC, which shifts to 532.66 eV after deposition of 1.8 nm of ITIC.

108 The C1s spectrum for bare sputtered TiO_x shows a peak at 284.50 eV and a shoulder at 285.70 eV,
109 originating from residual carbon surface contamination of the oxide surface. After deposition of 0.5
110 nm ITIC, a larger peak is observed at binding energy 285.00 eV with a shoulder at 286.00 eV. After
111 deposition of 0.9 nm of ITIC, the main C1s peak moves to 285.11 eV, and further to 285.17 eV after

112 deposition of 1.8 nm of ITIC. The yellow graph in figure 1c is the C1s spectrum for ex-situ prepared
 113 (spin-coated) ITIC on Au measured at ASTRID2. It shows a main C1s peak at 284.93 eV with a
 114 higher BE shoulder at 286.51 eV.

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117 **Figure 1.** a) Ti 2p, b) O 1s and c) C 1s core levels for sputtered TiO_x before and after deposition of
 118 0.5 nm, 0.9 nm and 1.8 nm of ITIC, C1a core level on spin coated ITIC film is displayed for
 119 comparison. A Shirley background¹⁹ has been subtracted from the spectra using CasaXPS²⁰. All
 120 spectra are measured using a photon energy of 650 eV.

121 Overall, the core levels show that there are no considerable shifts in the BE of the Ti 2p and O1s main
 122 peaks upon ITIC deposition, however a small shift of 0.17 eV to higher BEs is observed for C1s when
 123 going from 0.5 nm to 1.8 nm ITIC thickness. In addition, the Ti 2p spectra show that oxidation of
 124 Ti³⁺ occurs upon ITIC deposition. This is on contrast to what has previously been observed for

125 fullerenes, which did not result in an oxidation of Ti^{3+} in atomic layer deposited anatase TiO_x ²¹. The
126 O1s spectra show the appearance of a new peak due to the oxygen present in the ITIC molecule at
127 532.66 eV for 1.8 nm of ITIC, which shifts to 532.40 eV at the interface with TiO_x . A similar shift is
128 also observed for the C 1s signal. The increased oxidation of Ti^{3+} , and the binding energy shift of O
129 1s and C 1s upon ITIC deposition, is consistent with the transfer of electrons from the TiO_x substrate
130 to the molecular layer at the interface.

131 Figure 2a shows the valence band spectra measured with $h\nu=140$ eV for TiO_x before and after spray
132 deposition of 0.9 nm and 1.8 nm of ITIC, and for spin coated ITIC on gold. The shape of the VB
133 spectra after ITIC deposition indicates that the signal is mainly dominated by the TiO_x substrate. For
134 the bare sputtered TiO_x and sprayed ITIC on TiO_x , a feature is observed around ~ 1 eV, which is
135 attributed to defect states in TiO_x originating from excess electrons in part filling the Ti 3d orbitals in
136 the surface and sub-surface region due to oxygen vacancies²². For the spin coated ITIC, two features
137 are observed in the valence band around 2 eV and 4 eV, which agrees with previous observations for
138 films prepared under similar conditions²³. The 1.8 nm sprayed ITIC on TiO_x displays a shoulder
139 around 4 eV, which could be related to the 4 eV feature observed for spin-coated ITIC. The valence
140 band maxima (VBMs) were determined to be 3.43 eV, 3.38 eV, 3.17 and 1.15 eV for bare sputtered
141 TiO_x , 0.9 nm ITIC, 1.8 nm ITIC on TiO_x and spin coated ITIC on gold, respectively. The large
142 difference in VBM for the spray-coated ITIC sample can be explained by their VB spectra being
143 dominated by the TiO_x substrate. A shift of 0.21 eV towards higher BEs is measured for the VBM
144 close to interface, which origin is complicated by the presence of a strong signal of the substrate. The
145 in-set in figure 2a shows that the 1 eV feature does not completely disappear after ITIC deposition,
146 but that it is strongly reduced. This could either originate from overlayer attenuation with ITIC
147 deposition or from an interfacial state. This will be discussed later.

148 RESPES at the C K-edge was performed on 0.9 nm ITIC on TiO_x to enhance the signal from the
149 carbon HOMO states, and evidence the presence of interfacial state having carbon character. The
150 RESPES spectra ON and OFF resonance can be seen in figure 2b. The ON-resonance photon energy
151 was chosen based on the NEXAFS spectrum observed in figure 2c, which shows one main feature at
152 285.2 eV attributed to transitions from C 1s to π^* orbitals¹¹. Therefore, the ON-resonance spectrum
153 has been recorded with $h\nu=285.2$ eV, while the OFF-resonance spectrum was recorded with $h\nu=282$
154 eV.

155 The OFF-resonance valence band is mainly dominated by the TiO_x substrate and is very similar to
156 the spectra in figure 2a. The ON-resonance spectrum is significantly different, which indicates that it
157 is dominated by the carbon orbitals. Here, a strong feature around ~ 4 eV is observed as in the valence
158 band of the spin coated sample, but no other feature at about 2 eV is evidenced, which could confirm
159 that such frontier orbitals possess other character than carbon. Moreover, the defect state feature
160 located at 1eV is still observed in the ON-resonance spectrum, similar to the OFF-resonance
161 spectrum, indicating that such state is more likely related to the substrate and not to an interfacial
162 state with carbon character.

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166 **Figure 2.** a) Valence bands ($h\nu=140$ eV) of sputtered TiO_x before and after deposition of 0.9 nm and
167 1.8 nm of ITIC, compared to spin-coated ITIC film valence band ($h\nu=50$ eV). The inset shows a
168 zoom of the 1 eV defect state and the green lines show the linear fits used to determine the VBM b)
169 RESPES at the C K-edge OFF and ON resonance for 0.9 nm ITIC on TiO_x , c) NEXAFS at the C K-
170 edge for 0.9 nm ITIC on TiO_x .

171 To determine whether the defect state present in the valence band at ~ 1 eV is originating solely from
172 the TiO_x , or if the carbon from ITIC also contributes to the intensity of this feature, the valence band
173 for 0.9 nm ITIC on TiO_x measured OFF-resonance at the C K-edge was subtracted from the ON-
174 resonance spectrum. The result is displayed in Figure 3a (red), which is compared to the valence band
175 of the spin coated film (yellow). After the subtraction, the 1 eV feature completely disappears,
176 supporting the fact that carbon does not contribute to the intensity at the defect state energy, and
177 confirms that there are no interfacial states originating from carbon contribution in the valence band

178 at the TiO_x/ITIC interface. The VBMs have here been determined to be 1.15 eV and 1.43 eV for spin
179 coated ITIC (hν=50 eV) and 0.9 nm sprayed ITIC on TiO_x (hν=285.2 eV), respectively. The VBM
180 of 1.15 eV for ex-situ prepared ITIC is comparable to what has previously been reported for other ex-
181 situ prepared NFAs¹². Both valence bands display a feature around ~4 eV, but the spin-coated ITIC
182 displays another feature around 2 eV that is not present in the spray-coated ITIC on TiO_x measured
183 at the C K-edge, which suggests that this feature does not have any carbon contribution originating
184 intrinsically from ITIC.

185 The LUMO part is given by the NEXAFS N-edge spectra for both sample preparations, i.e. spray
186 deposition on TiO_x (red) and spin coating on gold (yellow), as seen in figure 3b. The two spectra look
187 very similar with a main feature at 399.7 eV, and two smaller features around ~398.6 eV and ~400.8
188 eV. The frontier orbitals in the LUMO measured at 398.6 eV, and better seen at the N K-edge than at
189 the C K-edge, support DFT calculations on similar molecules, suggesting that they are dominated by
190 the end groups of the acceptors²⁴.

191

199 **Figure 3.** a) Red: RESPES ON-resonance VB spectrum of 0.9 nm ITIC on sputtered TiO_x after
200 subtraction of the OFF-resonance spectrum. Yellow: VB for spin coated ITIC measured with $h\nu=50$
201 eV, b) Red :NEXAFS N-edge spectrum for 0.9 nm sprayed ITIC on sputtered TiO_x. Yellow :
202 NEXAFS N-edge spectrum for spin coated ITIC.

203 To better understand the interplay between ITIC and TiO_x, and to study how the ITIC overlayer
204 affects the defect states of TiO_x, RESPES was also performed at the Ti L-edge. When tuning the
205 photon energy in the vicinity of the Ti L-edge, the Ti 2p to Ti 3d transitions are enhanced, which
206 provides information about the electronic structure of the ground-state of the 3d orbitals in TiO_x²⁵.

207 Figure 4a shows the NEXAFS Ti L-edge spectra for bare sputtered TiO_x, and for the 0.9 nm ITIC on
208 sputtered TiO_x. The two spectra are almost identical, and both display two main features below 462
209 eV (458.0 eV and 459.7 eV) arising from electron transitions from Ti 2p_{3/2} core-level, and two more
210 features above 462 eV due to Ti 2p spin-orbit splitting corresponding to electron transitions from Ti
211 2p_{1/2} core-level. The feature at 458.0 eV is a result of transition from the Ti 2p_{3/2} orbital to the 3d e_g
212 sub-band, while the feature at 459.7 eV corresponds to transition from Ti 2p_{2/3} to the 3d t_{2g} sub-
213 band²⁶. The photon energy was tuned to these two values to measure the valence bands ON-
214 resonance, and compared with valence band measured with photon energy 450 eV (OFF-resonance).

215 Figure 4b shows the RESPES spectra at the two resonances and OFF-resonance, for the bare
216 sputtered TiO_x and for the 0.9 nm of ITIC on TiO_x. For both samples, it is seen that the signal from
217 the TiO_x is enhanced ON-resonance, especially the 1 eV defect state. Contrarily to the case of
218 fullerene on sputtered TiO_x²⁷, RESPES spectra in figure 4b show that the d-states in TiO_x are not
219 completely quenched by the non-fullerene acceptor ITIC. This is a major difference that could
220 potentially indicate why photocatalytic decomposition of the acceptor by the metal oxide ETLs in

221 OPV is an issue only for NFAs (here ITIC), and not fullerene acceptors⁴. We emphasize that the
 222 defect state is here partially quenched by the ITIC overlayer, and a further discussion on this follows.

223 To better understand the specificity of the sputtered TiO_x interface, a natural anatase TiO_x single
 224 crystal has also been studied before and after spray deposition of ITIC. Figure 4c shows the NEXAFS
 225 Ti L-edge spectra for the anatase crystal before and after deposition of 1.2 nm of ITIC. The spectrum
 226 measured on the anatase surface is similar to already published spectra of such structural phase²⁶,
 227 whereas the anatase/ITIC spectrum is comparable with the spectra in figure 4a measured on sputtered
 228 TiO_x/ITIC with two resonances at ~458.0 eV +/- 0.1 eV and ~459.7 eV +/- 0.1 eV. Figure 4d shows
 229 the Ti L-edge RESPES spectra for this sample. Again, it is seen that the 1 eV state is enhanced
 230 significantly ON-resonance, however the defect state looks different for the bare anatase crystal, when
 231 compared to the sputtered TiO_x (figure 4b). For the anatase crystal, the 1 eV defect seems to have a
 232 shoulder close to the Fermi level, which is not observed for sputtered TiO_x. After deposition of ITIC,
 233 this shoulder disappears and the RESPES for anatase/ITIC looks more similar to sputtered TiO_x/ITIC.

234

235

236 **Figure 4** a) NEXAFS Ti L-edge for sputtered TiO_x before and after ITIC deposition, b) RESPES at
237 Ti L edge for TiO_x before and after ITIC depositions, c) NEXAFS Ti L-edge for single anatase TiO_x
238 crystal before and after ITIC deposition, d) RESPES at Ti L-edge for anatase TiO_x before and after
239 ITIC deposition.

240 Figures 5a-5d show a zoom of the 1 eV defect state along with deconvolutions for sputtered (TiO_x)
241 (5a), anatase TiO_x (5c), sputtered TiO_x / ITIC (5b) and anatase TiO_x /ITIC (5d) at $h\nu=458.0$ eV.

242 When fitting the 1 eV defect state for sputtered TiO_x before and after ITIC deposition, it appears that
243 two features are needed to adjust the defect state; a lower BE feature (0.8 eV-1 eV), which is attributed
244 to sub-surface defects, and a higher BE feature (1.2 eV-1.4 eV), originating from surface oxygen
245 vacancies^{16, 28, 29}. The defect states with deconvolutions for sputtered TiO_x before and after ITIC
246 deposition are seen in figure 5a-5b. These figures show that for sputtered TiO_x , the 1 eV feature is
247 dominated by surface oxygen vacancies for the 3d e_g orbital (458.0 eV). After ITIC deposition,
248 surface oxygen vacancies are still dominating, and now to a larger extent (see table 1).

249 For anatase TiO_x , before deposition of ITIC, two features are observed in the defect state: a broad
250 peak state at around 0.9 eV that can be deconvoluted with two components as for sputtered TiO_x and
251 a low BE shallow gap state at 0.13 eV appearing at crystal edges, which is not present in sputtered

252 TiO_x. This is similar to what has previously been reported on anatase single crystals³⁰. After ITIC
253 deposition, a broad peak centered around 1.2 eV can be well adjusted with two features at 1.1 eV
254 (sub-surface defects) and 1.4-1.6 eV (surface defects)²⁸, similar to the sputtered TiO_x/ITIC. It is worth
255 noting that before and after ITIC deposition, about 50 % surface defects and 50 % sub-surface defects
256 are evidenced, for anatase TiO_x, which is significantly different from the sputtered TiO_x/ITIC. Table
257 1 shows the relative amounts of surface and sub-surface defects in sputtered and anatase TiO_x before
258 and after ITIC deposition.

259

260

261 **Figure 5.** Deconvolution of 1 eV defect state for $h\nu=458$ eV for a) sputtered TiO_x, b) 0.9 nm ITIC on
262 sputtered TiO_x c) anatase TiO_x, d) 1.2 nm ITIC on anatase TiO_x.

263 The difference observed in the defect state region before and after ITIC deposition on sputtered TiO_x
264 and anatase TiO_x can explain the limited photocatalytic degradation evidenced in sputtered TiO_x/ITIC
265 based OPV devices. Indeed, oxygen vacancies in sputtered TiO_x lie mostly in the surface region,
266 which contrasts the anatase TiO_x where an equal distribution between surface and sub-surface defects
267 is observed. In addition sub-surface defects are partially quenched after ITIC deposition on sputtered

268 TiO_x (see Table 1), whereas no significant change in the surface defects is observed in the case of
 269 anatase TiO_x, enabling them to contribute to the photocatalysis process^{18,31}. Such a picture is
 270 reinforced by our previous study of sputtered TiO_x/C70 in which a complete quenching of the defect
 271 state was observed upon C70 deposition²⁷ and that photocatalytic decomposition in OPV devices is
 272 typically not observed at fullerene/TiO_x ETL interfaces.

273 **Table 1.** Relative surface and sub-surface defect contributions to the 1 eV defect peak in sputtered
 274 and anatase TiO_x before and after deposition of ITIC. The results are extracted from fit of RESPES
 275 Ti L-edge data presented in Figure5.

276

Material	Photon energy	%Sub-surface defects	% Surface defects
Sputtered TiO _x	458.0 eV	26.4 % +/- 0.6 %	73.4 % +/- 1.5 %
0.9 nm ITIC on sputtered TiO _x	458.0 eV	17.7 % +/- 0.4 %	82.3 % +/- 1.6 %
Anatase TiO _x	458.0 eV	50.4 % +/- 1 %	49.6 % +/-1 %
1.2 nm ITIC on anatase TiO _x	458.0 eV	50.0 % +/- 1 %	50.0 % +/- 1 %

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279 CONCLUSIONS

280 In this study, we have investigated by in-situ photoemission and absorption spectroscopy the interface
 281 between TiO_x, both sputter-deposited and a single anatase TiO_x crystal, and the NFA molecule ITIC,
 282 to understand the electronic state interplay at this interface. Recently, such sputter-deposited TiO_x
 283 electron transport layers have shown decreased photocatalytic decomposition of ITIC molecules,
 284 resulting in stable PBDB-T:ITIC based organic solar cells¹⁰. We have here shown that in-situ
 285 deposition of ITIC molecules on sputtered TiO_x resulted in oxidation of Ti³⁺, and the emergence of a

286 new O1s peak, which shifts to lower BE when increasing the thickness of ITIC. This is consistent
287 with charge transfer between the Ti^{3+} and the oxygen in ITIC. The in-situ prepared ITIC was
288 compared to ex-situ prepared ITIC, and we observed differences in the C1s binding energies (0.24
289 eV) and the valence band maxima (0.28 eV), while the N K edge spectra were similar for the two
290 ITIC. The in-situ prepared ITIC had a VBM of 1.43 eV, while the ex-situ prepared ITIC on gold had
291 a VBM of 1.15 eV.

292 Furthermore, we have used RESPES photoemission studies to study the surface defects observed in
293 the valence band at about 1 eV. We demonstrate that oxygen vacancies in sputtered TiO_x lie mostly
294 in the surface region, which contrasts the anatase TiO_x where an equal distribution between surface
295 and sub-surface oxygen vacancies is observed. Furthermore, we show that sub-surface defects, which
296 are known to have a strong photocatalytic activity, are not affected by ITIC deposition on anatase
297 TiO_x , whereas they are partially quenched in the case of the sputtered TiO_x . Such a difference could
298 explain why the sputter-deposited TiO_x demonstrates inferior photocatalytic activity and does not
299 show a strong photocatalytic degradation of ITIC molecules in organic solar cell, leading to
300 significantly prolonged device lifetimes.

301 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

302 All photoemission and absorption measurements of sputtered TiO_x , anatase TiO_x crystal and spray
303 deposited ITIC were performed at the FlexPES (Flexible Photoelectron Spectroscopy) beamline at
304 the MAXIV synchrotron in Sweden and all the measurements performed on spin coated ITIC were
305 recorded at the MatLine beamline at the Danish synchrotron ASTRID2. Details on beamlines and
306 experimental set-up can be found in Ref.³². and Ref.³³ for FlexPES and MatLine respectively.

307

308 *Sputtering of TiO_x thin films*

309 TiO_x films were sputter-deposited on ITO substrates at University of Southern Denmark. The films
310 were sputtered in argon plasma from a white TiO₂ target (99.99 % purity) from Kurt Lesker. The ITO
311 substrates (approx. 15Ω/square sheet resistance) from Kintec were annealed at 150°C for 30 min
312 before the deposition. The TiO_x was then deposited on top of the ITO films with a sputtering power
313 of 300 W at a pressure of 3·10⁻³ mbar while keeping the substrate temperature at 150°C. After the
314 deposition, the substrates were cooled in the presence of 5 sccm of oxygen inside the sputter chamber,
315 for around 1 h. The full deposition and cooling process was performed in a Cryofox cluster UHV
316 deposition system from Polyteknik A/S. This deposition method has been described previously¹⁰. The
317 sputtered TiO_x films were loaded into the preparation chamber at the FlexPES beamline where they
318 were annealed at 150°C for 30 min and cooled in the presence of oxygen with a pressure of around
319 1.5·10⁻⁶ mbar and subsequently transferred to the measurement chamber for photoemission and
320 absorption measurements.

321 *Preparation of TiO₂ anatase single crystal*

322 Before ITIC deposition, the single crystal anatase sample was Ar sputtered for 30 mins and annealed
323 at 560°C at the FlexPES beamline.

324 *Photoemission and absorption measurements at FlexPES*

325 The high-resolution XPS, UPS and RESPES experiments were carried out at the FlexPES beamline
326 at MAX IV on the Surface and Material Science setup³². The end station was equipped with a Scienta
327 SES-2002 analyzer, two preparation chambers, sample transfer and treatment facilities, and a fast
328 entry chamber with a sample garage.

329 XAS measurements were performed at the FlexPES beamline, with horizontally linear polarized light
330 in the energy range of 40–1500 eV. Defocused beam spot size resulting in 2 × 1mm spot on the sample
331 was used to minimize any possible radiation damage. The energy resolution was about 20 meV and

332 50 meV at photon energies close to the C K-edge and Ti L-edge respectively. XAS spectra were
333 collected in partial electron yield (PEY) detection modes with microchannel plate.

334 *Spray deposition of ITIC*

335 A UHV spray deposition tool from MolecularSpray with three vacuum stages was used to do spray
336 deposition of ITIC in situ. The spray tool was mounted on the load-lock of the FlexPES beamline
337 endstation allowing vacuum deposition. A 100 ug/mL solution of ITIC (Brilliant Matters) in
338 chlorobenzene was prepared and stirred at 80°C before it was injected into the spray deposition tool
339 with a speed of 5 mL/h using a glass syringe and a NE-300 Just Infusion Syringe Pump. The TiO_x
340 films were transferred from vacuum preparation chamber after annealing in oxygen to the load-lock
341 , where ITIC was spray deposited on top.

342 *Spin coated ITIC*

343 The spin-coated ITIC sample was prepared by spin-coating a 5 mg/mL ITIC (Brilliant Matters)
344 solution in chlorobenzene (Sigma-Aldrich) on a gold substrate using a rotation speed of 2600 rpm,
345 which results in a thick film.

346 *Data analysis*

347 The thickness of the ITIC overlayer was determined by intensity attenuation of the TiO_x substrate
348 following the procedure described in ¹³.

349 Photon energy have been calibrated using gold sample mounted on the same manipulator assuming
350 Au 4f_{7/2} core-level BE at 84.0 eV³⁴ and also by measuring this line in second order light from the
351 monochromator.

352 The NEXAFS spectra recorded at FlexPES were normalized using the ring current recorded on a gold
353 mesh after the exit slit of the monochromator.

354 Core levels were fitted with Gaussian functions using Igor Pro software and a Shirley background¹⁹
355 was subtracted using CasaXPS prior to fitting.

356 The defect state in the valence band was fitted using CasaXPS. First, a Shirley background was
357 subtracted followed by fitting of GL(50) Voigt functions with 50 % Gaussian and Lorentzian
358 contributions. For sake of clarity, the shallow gap state present in the anatase TiO_x that should be a
359 composition of a Gaussian and a Fermi-Dirac function as shown in Ref³¹, has been adjusted by a
360 Voigt function located at 0.1 eV BE.

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365 SUPPORTING INFORMATION

- 366 • NEXAFS N K edge and S L edge spectra for sprayed ITIC on sputtered TiO_x and
367 deconvolution of the 1 eV defect state for sputtered and anatase TiO_x before and after ITIC
368 deposition measured with photon energy 459.7 eV.

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